

R Notebook

```
library(knitr)
# Set so that long lines in R will be wrapped:
opts_chunk$set(tidy.opts=list(width.cutoff=40),tidy=TRUE)
```

Content

1. convert csv file into points
2. curate data -critical_binary -biodiversity indicator
-ecological zone -watershed biodiversity score -hydrography distance -road distance -recent fire -elevation
-patch analysis
3. combine all environmental data & save to csv file
4. combine tick and pathogen data

Notes

-this builds on the data that was previously curated based on tick collections -instead of using ArcMap, this is the code to do GIS work in R -codes need to be modified for any year added -pathogen and tick datasets are distinct, need to combine tick and pathogen data together -edit file path

library

```
library(data.table)
library(tm)
library(tibble)
library(stringr)
library(textreg)
# landscape libraries
library(ncdf4)
library(maptools)
library(raster)
library(rgdal)
library(SDMTools)
```

1. convert csv file into points

-convert geographical coordinates

get tick data

```
tick <- read.csv(".csv", header = TRUE, check.names = FALSE)
```

turn csv into points

```
library(sf)
new <- "+proj=longlat +ellps=WGS84 +datum=WGS84 +no_defs"

pts_tick <- SpatialPoints(tick[, c("LONG",
  "LAT")])
proj4string(pts_tick) <- CRS(new)
pts_tick_sf <- st_as_sf(tick[, c("LONG",
  "LAT")], coords = c("LONG", "LAT"), crs = 4326)
```

```
assign("pts_tick_sf", st_transform(pts_tick_sf,
  crs = 26918))
```

2. curate data

-reproject environmental data -NLCD: crop to cover NYS extent and reproject so it is in WGS 1984 projection (analysis in ArcMap) -biodiversity raster also reprojected in ArcMap

critical

```
# reproject file
crit <- readOGR("/Critical_Env_Areas_20160708.shp")
crit_p <- spTransform(crit, new)
save(crit_p, file = "/crit_p.Rout")

# extract data
load("/crit_p.Rout")

system.time({
  temp_crit <- sp::over(pts_tick, crit_p)
})
tick$critical_binary <- 0
tick[which(!is.na(temp_crit$NAME)), "critical_binary"] <- 1

sum(is.na(tick$critical_binary))
```

biodiversity

```
library(velox)
library(prioritizr)
biod <- raster("/biodiver_proj1.tif")

system.time({
  extract_biod <- fast_extract(biod, pts_tick,
    velox = TRUE)
})

tick$BIOD_RASTERVALU <- extract_biod
```

ecozone

```
ecozone <- readOGR("/dfw_ecozone.shp")
proj4string(ecozone)
eco_p <- spTransform(ecozone, new)
save(eco_p, file = "eco_p.Rout")

load("/eco_p.Rout")

system.time({
  extract_ecozone <- sp::over(pts_tick,
    eco_p)
})

temp_eco <- as.character(extract_ecozone$MINOR_NUM)
temp_ecoOri <- temp_eco
```

```

temp_eco1 <- as.character(extract_ecozone1$MINOR_NUM)
temp_ecoOri1 <- temp_eco1

sort(unique(temp_ecoOri))
sort(unique(temp_ecoOri1))

As <- c("A01", "A02", "A03", "A04", "A05",
        "A06", "A07", "A08", "A09", "A10")
Bs <- c("B01", "B02", "B03", "B04")
Cs <- c("C01")
Ds <- c("D01", "D02")
Es <- c("E01", "E02", "E03")
Fs <- c("F01")
Gs <- c("G01")
Hs <- c("H01")
Is <- c("I01")
Js <- c("J01", "J02", "J03", "J04", "J05",
        "J06", "J07")
Ks <- c("K01", "K02", "K03", "K04", "K05",
        "K06", "K07")
Ls <- c("L01", "L02")

temp_eco[which(temp_eco %in% As)] <- 1
temp_eco[which(temp_eco %in% Bs)] <- 2
temp_eco[which(temp_eco %in% Cs)] <- 3
temp_eco[which(temp_eco %in% Ds)] <- 4
temp_eco[which(temp_eco %in% Es)] <- 5
temp_eco[which(temp_eco %in% Fs)] <- 6
temp_eco[which(temp_eco %in% Gs)] <- 7
temp_eco[which(temp_eco %in% Hs)] <- 8
temp_eco[which(temp_eco %in% Is)] <- 9
temp_eco[which(temp_eco %in% Js)] <- 10
temp_eco[which(temp_eco %in% Ks)] <- 11
temp_eco[which(temp_eco %in% Ls)] <- 12

temp_eco1[which(temp_eco1 %in% As)] <- 1
temp_eco1[which(temp_eco1 %in% Bs)] <- 2
temp_eco1[which(temp_eco1 %in% Cs)] <- 3
temp_eco1[which(temp_eco1 %in% Ds)] <- 4
temp_eco1[which(temp_eco1 %in% Es)] <- 5
temp_eco1[which(temp_eco1 %in% Fs)] <- 6
temp_eco1[which(temp_eco1 %in% Gs)] <- 7
temp_eco1[which(temp_eco1 %in% Hs)] <- 8
temp_eco1[which(temp_eco1 %in% Is)] <- 9
temp_eco1[which(temp_eco1 %in% Js)] <- 10
temp_eco1[which(temp_eco1 %in% Ks)] <- 11
temp_eco1[which(temp_eco1 %in% Ls)] <- 12

tick$ecozone_major <- temp_eco
tick$ecozone_major <- as.integer(tick$ecozone_major)

```

waterBioSc

```

# reproject water to proper CRS
water <- readOGR("/Watershed_Biodiversity_Score.shp")
proj4string(water)
water_p <- spTransform(water, new)
save(water_p, file = "/water_p.Rout")

load("/water_p.Rout")
system.time({
  temp_water <- sp::over(pts_tick, water_p)
})

tick$waterBioSc <- temp_water$Score

```

hydro

```

library(dplyr)
hydro <- st_read("/AreaHydrography.shp")
hydro_sf <- st_transform(hydro, crs = 26918)

# create an index of the nearest feature
index <- st_nearest_feature(x = pts_tick_sf,
  y = hydro_sf)
# slice based on the index
slice_hydro <- hydro_sf %>% slice(index)
# calculate distance between polygons
poly_dist <- st_distance(x = pts_tick_sf,
  y = slice_hydro, by_element = TRUE)
# add dist to original Lat/Long file
tick$Hydro_NEAR_DIST <- as.numeric(poly_dist)

```

Road a. 2000-2013 (2013) b. 2014-2017 (2015) c. 2018+ (2018)

```

road18 <- st_read("/t1_2018_36_prisecroads/t1_2018_36_prisecroads.shp")
road15 <- st_read("/t1_2015_36_prisecroads/t1_2015_36_prisecroads.shp")
road13 <- st_read("/t1_2013_36_prisecroads/t1_2013_36_prisecroads.shp")

table(tick$Year)

road18_sf <- st_transform(road18, crs = 26918)
road15_sf <- st_transform(road15, crs = 26918)
road13_sf <- st_transform(road13, crs = 26918)

tmp_tick13 <- tick[which(tick$Year <= 2013),
  ]
tmp_tick15 <- tick[which(tick$Year <= 2017 &
  tick$Year > 2013), ]
tmp_tick18 <- tick[which(tick$Year == 2018),
  ]

pts_tick_sf13 <- st_as_sf(tmp_tick13[, c("LONG",
  "LAT")], coords = c("LONG", "LAT"), crs = 4326)
assign("pts_tick_sf13", st_transform(pts_tick_sf13,
  crs = 26918))

pts_tick_sf15 <- st_as_sf(tmp_tick15[, c("LONG",

```

```

    "LAT"]], coords = c("LONG", "LAT"), crs = 4326)
assign("pts_tick_sf15", st_transform(pts_tick_sf15,
  crs = 26918))

pts_tick_sf18 <- st_as_sf(tmp_tick18[, c("LONG",
  "LAT")], coords = c("LONG", "LAT"), crs = 4326)
assign("pts_tick_sf18", st_transform(pts_tick_sf18,
  crs = 26918))

# road13 (repeat this code for road 15/18
# & pts13 & pts15)
system.time({
  # create an index of the nearest feature
  index <- st_nearest_feature(x = pts_tick_sf13,
    y = road13_sf)
  # slice based on the index (slice isn't
  # that unique)
  slice_road <- road13_sf %>% slice(index)
  # calculate distance between polygons
  poly_dist <- st_distance(x = pts_tick_sf13,
    y = slice_road, by_element = TRUE)
  # add type of road & road dist to
  # original Lat/Long file
  tmp_tick13$road_NEAR_DIST <- as.numeric(poly_dist)

  road_C <- as.character(road13$MTFCC[index])
  road_C[which(road_C == "S1100")] <- 1
  road_C[which(road_C == "S1200")] <- 2
  tmp_tick13$road_class <- road_C

  road_T <- as.character(road13$RTTYP[index])
  road_T[which(road_T == "C")] <- 1
  road_T[which(road_T == "I")] <- 2
  road_T[which(road_T == "M")] <- 3
  road_T[which(road_T == "S")] <- 4
  road_T[which(road_T == "Q")] <- 4
  road_T[which(road_T == "U")] <- 5
  tmp_tick13$road_type <- road_T
})

# add to data frame
tmp_tick <- rbind(tmp_tick13, tmp_tick15,
  tmp_tick18)
tick <- tmp_tick
tick$road_class <- as.numeric(tick$road_class)
tick$road_type <- as.numeric(tick$road_type)

```

fire

```
fire <- read.csv("/2000_2019_NYSWildfireData/2000_2019_NYSWildfiredata.csv")
```

```

# add year, month of fire
Chdate <- as.character(fire$FireDiscoveryDate)
Chdate <- as.Date(Chdate)
Chdate_year <- substr(Chdate, 1, 4)
fire <- cbind(fire, Chdate_year)
names(fire)[length(names(fire))] <- "Year"
fire$Year <- as.numeric(as.character(fire$Year))
# month
Chdate_month <- gsub(".*[-](^[^.]*)[-].*",
  "\\1", Chdate)
fire <- cbind(fire, Chdate_month)
names(fire)[length(names(fire))] <- "month"
fire$month <- as.numeric(as.character(fire$month))
# county
fire$County <- as.character(fire$County)

fire_sf <- st_as_sf(fire[, c("Longitude",
  "Latitude")], coords = c("Longitude",
  "Latitude"), crs = 4269)
assign("fire_sf", st_transform(fire_sf, crs = 26918))

pts_tick_buff <- sf::st_buffer(pts_tick_sf,
  2500)
temp_int_tick <- sf::st_intersects(pts_tick_buff,
  fire_sf)

# n_fire_t0
tick$n_fire_t0 <- 0
tick$n_fire_t1 <- 0
tick$n_fire_t2 <- 0

for (row in 1:nrow(temp_int_tick)) {
  temp1 <- temp_int_tick[[row]]
  temp_r <- fire[temp1, ]
  no_fires <- temp_r[which(temp_r$Year ==
    tick$Year[row]), ]
  no_fires1 <- temp_r[which(temp_r$Year ==
    (tick$Year[row] - 1)), ]
  no_fires2 <- temp_r[which(temp_r$Year ==
    (tick$Year[row] - 2)), ]
  if (nrow(no_fires) > 0) {
    tick$n_fire_t0[row] <- nrow(no_fires)
  }
  if (nrow(no_fires1) > 0) {
    tick$n_fire_t1[row] <- nrow(no_fires1)
  }
  if (nrow(no_fires2) > 0) {
    tick$n_fire_t2[row] <- nrow(no_fires2)
  }
}

summary(tick$n_fire_t0)
summary(tick$n_fire_t1)

```

```
summary(tick$n_fire_t2)
```

elevation -download USGS NED Img files and combine into one folder

```
# project elevation list all tiles
setwd("/elevation/all_files")
img <- list.files(pattern = ".img$")
n.img <- length(img)
find.list <- str_match(img, ".*13_(.*?)_IMG.*|img(.*?)_13.*")
new_list <- append(find.list[1:3, 3], find.list[4:n.img,
  2])
new_list

for (n in 1:45) {
  print(paste("starting", n))
  temp_img.p <- projectRaster(raster(img[n]),
    crs = new)
  print("finish project")
  writeRaster(temp_img.p, filename = paste0("/output/elev_proj/",
    new_list[n], "_proj.envi"), bylayer = TRUE,
    format = "ENVI")
  print("save raster project as envi")
}

# get elevation files
setwd("/output/elev_proj")
list.proj <- list.files("/output/elev_proj/",
  pattern = ".envi$")
for (n in 1:length(list.proj)) {
  assign(paste0("rast", n), raster(list.proj[n]))
}

tick$elevation <- NA

# which rast files does it intersect
# with? (determines which tiles to
# search)
rast_intersect_tick <- c()
for (n in 1:length(list.proj)) {
  if (!is.null(intersect(extent(get(paste0("rast",
    n))), pts_tick))) {
    rast_intersect_tick <- append(rast_intersect_tick,
      n)
  }
}
list.proj[rast_intersect_tick]

# extract elevation
eleToMerge_tick <- data.frame(matrix(ncol = length(rast_intersect_tick),
  nrow = nrow(tick)))
for (n in 1:length(rast_intersect_tick)) {
  eleToMerge_tick[, n] <- fast_extract(get(paste0("rast",
    rast_intersect_tick[n])), pts_tick,
    velox = TRUE)
```

```

}

# clean up into a single column
library(tidyrr)
# some cols have zero values; remove as
# needed for ease edit these Xs as needed
final_ele_tick <- eleToMerge_tick %>% mutate(mycol = coalesce(X3,
  X4, X5, X6, X10, X11, X12, X19, X20,
  X21, X22, X23, X24, X25, X27, X28, X29,
  X30, X31, X32, X34, X35, X36, X37)) %>%
  select(mycol)

tick$elevation <- final_ele_tick[, 1]

NLCD patches
LatLon <- data.frame(tick[, c("Longitude",
  "Latitude")])
map2016 <- raster("/NLCD/proj2016.tif")

# reclassify all sub-landscape types into
# one
r.omance <- function(x) {
  x[x %in% 10:19] <- 10
  x[x %in% 20:29] <- 20
  x[x %in% 30:39] <- 30
  x[x %in% 40:49] <- 40
  x[x %in% 50:59] <- 50
  x[x %in% 70:79] <- 70
  x[x %in% 80:89] <- 80
  x[x %in% 90:99] <- 90
  return(x)
}

reclass2016 <- calc(map2016, fun = r.omance)

# calculate forest patches
library(sp)

# make spatial points class
llCRS <- CRS("+proj=longlat +ellps=WGS84 +datum=WGS84 +no_defs")
LL <- SpatialPoints(LatLon, proj4string = llCRS)

library(geobuffer)

tick$edge.density50 <- 0
tick$edge.density100 <- 0
tick$edge.density500 <- 0

tick$patch.cohesion.index50 <- 0
tick$patch.cohesion.index100 <- 0
tick$patch.cohesion.index500 <- 0

for (pt in 1:nrow(tick)) {

```

```

# geodesic buffering
buffers_50m <- geobuffer_pts(xy = LL[pt,
  ], dist_m = c(50), output = "sf")
buffers_100m <- geobuffer_pts(xy = LL[pt,
  ], dist_m = c(100), output = "sf")
buffers_500m <- geobuffer_pts(xy = LL[pt,
  ], dist_m = c(500), output = "sf")

# use the right map for the right year
if (tick[pt, "Year"] >= 2016) {
  UseMap <- reclass2016
}
# crop map so analyses are faster
map50.sub <- crop(UseMap, extent(buffers_50m))
map100.sub <- crop(UseMap, extent(buffers_100m))
map500.sub <- crop(UseMap, extent(buffers_500m))

# mask to obtain raster within these
# circles
rr50 <- mask(map50.sub, buffers_50m)
rr100 <- mask(map100.sub, buffers_100m)
rr500 <- mask(map500.sub, buffers_500m)

# landscape statistics
test50 <- ClassStat(rr50)
test100 <- ClassStat(rr100)
test500 <- ClassStat(rr500)

if (length(test50$edge.density[which(test50$class ==
  40)]) > 0) {
  tick$edge.density50[pt] <- test50$edge.density[which(test50$class ==
    40)]
}
if (length(test100$edge.density[which(test100$class ==
  40)]) > 0) {
  tick$edge.density100[pt] <- test100$edge.density[which(test100$class ==
    40)]
}
if (length(test500$edge.density[which(test500$class ==
  40)]) > 0) {
  tick$edge.density500[pt] <- test500$edge.density[which(test500$class ==
    40)]
}

if (length(test50$patch.cohesion.index[which(test50$class ==
  40)]) > 0) {
  tick$patch.cohesion.index50[pt] <- test50$patch.cohesion.index[which(test50$class ==
    40)]
}
if (length(test100$patch.cohesion.index[which(test100$class ==
  40)]) > 0) {
  tick$patch.cohesion.index100[pt] <- test100$patch.cohesion.index[which(test100$class ==
    40)]
}

```

```

}
if (length(test500$patch.cohesion.index[which(test500$class ==
40)]) > 0) {
  tick$patch.cohesion.index500[pt] <- test500$patch.cohesion.index[which(test500$class ==
40)]
}
}

# 0 when no patches of class 40 (forest);
# NaN when ie single patches of forest
for (col in 1:ncol(tick)) {
  n <- sum(is.na(tick[, col]))
  if (n > 0) {
    print(paste(col, colnames(tick[col]),
n))
"/n"
}
}

tick[which(is.na(tick$patch.cohesion.index50 ==
0)), "patch.cohesion.index50"] <- 0
tick[which(is.na(tick$patch.cohesion.index100 ==
0)), "patch.cohesion.index100"] <- 0
tick[which(is.na(tick$patch.cohesion.index500 ==
0)), "patch.cohesion.index500"] <- 0

```

3. combine and save data

-turkey code: use bear/deer code; also recall that human population estimates are updated each year by Census Bureau -combine files with other previously curated variables, i.e. combine columns

```

library(data.table)
dataOri <- cbind(tick) #add other variables as needed
write.csv(dataOri, ".csv")

```

4. combine tick + pathogen data

```

library(lubridate) #to convert dates

```

Curate infected tick data

```

# match the environmental data with the
# pathogen data

# tick & env data (as curated above)
colnames(data_Ori)[1] <- "row_num"

# pathogen data
data_OriP <- read.csv(file = ".csv", check.names = FALSE,
header = TRUE)
Path_ori <- read.csv(file = ".csv", check.names = FALSE,
header = TRUE) #example of a later year when pathogen data is no longer in the same format

```

-Depending on the year, NYSDOH raw data is already summarized by site whereas in other years, each tested tick is a separate row -for the latter situation, edit pathogen data so they match other years

```
# rename data_OriP and remove first row
colnames(data_OriP) <- c("Date", "County",
  "Location", "total_tested", "BB_Neg",
  "BB_Pos")
# change classes
data_OriP[, "County"] <- as.character(data_OriP[,
  "County"])
data_OriP[, "Location"] <- as.character(data_OriP[,
  "Location"])
data_OriP[, "BB_Neg"] <- as.numeric(as.character(data_OriP[,
  "BB_Neg"]))
data_OriP[, "BB_Pos"] <- as.numeric(as.character(data_OriP[,
  "BB_Pos"]))

# change class for Path_ori
Path_ori1 <- Path_ori
Path_ori1[, "County"] <- as.character(Path_ori1[,
  "County"])
Path_ori1[, "Location"] <- as.character(Path_ori1[,
  "Location"])
# some of the Counties have spaces, such
# as
Path_ori1[which(Path_ori1$County != "St Lawrence"),
  "County"] <- gsub(" ", "", Path_ori1[which(Path_ori1$County !=
  "St Lawrence"), "County"])
```

raw pathogen data -group pathogen data together when it's not summarized -once data is summarized, can follow rest of code

```
# unique sites/date of collection for
# I.S. nymphs
Path_ori_Nymph <- Path_ori1[which((Path_ori1$Stage ==
  "Nymph") & (Path_ori1$Species == "I. scapularis")),
  ]

temp_sites <- unique(Path_ori_Nymph[, c("County",
  "Date Collected", "Location")])

Path <- data.frame(matrix(nrow = nrow(temp_sites),
  ncol = 10))
colnames(Path) <- c("Date", "County", "Location",
  "total_tested", "BB_Neg")

Path[, c("County", "Date", "Location")] <- temp_sites[,
  c("County", "Date Collected", "Location")]

for (row in 1:nrow(Path)) {
  temp <- Path_ori_Nymph[which((Path_ori_Nymph$County ==
  Path$County[row]) & (Path_ori_Nymph$`Date Collected` ==
  Path$Date[row]) & (Path_ori_Nymph$Location ==
  Path$Location[row])), ]
}
```

```

Path[row, "total_tested"] <- nrow(temp)
Path[row, "BB_Neg"] <- sum(temp$pcr_final_result_BB ==
  "N")
Path[row, "BB_Pos"] <- sum(temp$pcr_final_result_BB ==
  "P")
}
Path

```

change class of environmental data

```

data_Ori$Date <- as.character(data_Ori$Date)
data_Ori$County <- as.character(data_Ori$County)
data_Ori$Location <- as.character(data_Ori$Location)
data_Ori$Town <- as.character(data_Ori$Town)
data_Ori$turkeyFall <- as.numeric(as.character(data_Ori$turkeyFall))
data_Ori$critical_binary <- as.factor(data_Ori$critical_binary)
data_Ori$ecozone_major <- as.factor(data_Ori$ecozone_major)
data_Ori$road_class <- as.factor(data_Ori$road_class)
data_Ori$road_type <- as.factor(data_Ori$road_type)

```

NA in pathogen data

```

# pathogen data
for (col in 1:ncol(data_OriP)) {
  n <- sum(is.na(data_OriP[, col]))
  if (n > 0) {
    print(paste(col, colnames(data_OriP[col]),
      n))
    "/n"
  }
}

data_OriP[which(is.na(data_OriP$BB_Neg)),
  "BB_Neg"] <- 0
temp_path <- c("BB")
for (p in 1:length(temp_path)) {
  temp <- which(is.na(data_OriP[, paste0(temp_path[p],
    "_Pos"])))
  for (n in 1:length(temp)) {
    if (data_OriP[temp[n], paste0(temp_path[p],
      "_Neg")] == data_OriP$total_tested[temp[n]]) {
      data_OriP[temp[n], paste0(temp_path[p],
        "_Pos")] <- 0
    }
  }
}
}

# pathogen data
sum(is.na(Path)) #0

```

data_OriP

```

# put Date in the same format for path +
# tick data
data_OriP$Date1 <- mdy(data_OriP$Date)
data_Ori$Date1 <- mdy(data_Ori$Date)

```

match the environmental and pathogen data

```
data <- left_join(data_OriP, CombData, by = c("Date1",  
      "County", "Location"))
```

remove variables

```
data[, c("Date.x", "Date.y")] <- NULL
```

check code for any edits or error -may require manual fixes

```
data[which(is.na(data$row_num)), c("County",  
      "Location", "total_tested", "Date1")] #this should = 0 if no error
```

save tick

```
write.csv(data, "DIN.csv")
```